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RESEARCH INTO PAIRED CASES OF RARE PATHOLOGIES IN PAEDIATRIC ORTHOPAEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY

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Summary. ¹Protsaylo M. D., ¹Zubnina Yu. O., ¹Hrehk A. G., ¹Svystun R. V., ²Korol V. V., ¹Hoshchynskiy P .V. **RESEARCH INTO PAIRED CASES OF RARE PATHOLOGIES IN PAEDIATRIC ORTHOPAEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY.** - ¹I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, ²CNCE “Ternopil City Children's Municipal Hospital”; e-mail: protsaylo@tdmu.edu.ua. The law of paired events, observed in various medical settings, refers to the phenomenon where, after witnessing a rare or exceptional event, similar occurrences tend to follow within a short period. This trend is particularly evident in fields such as paediatric orthopaedics and traumatology. The objective of the research is to investigate such paired events, particularly focusing

on rare musculoskeletal pathologies in children. The study analyzed outpatient and inpatient records from the Ternopil Regional Children Clinic Hospital, using methods such as X-ray, MRI, and classical morphometric techniques to observe trends in rare clinical cases. The research uncovered multiple instances of paired cases, including two children with osteogenic sarcoma of the femur diagnosed within a two-month period. One case involved a 17-year-old girl with significant symptoms, including cancer cachexia and severe leg pain, leading to a diagnosis of osteogenic sarcoma. Two months later, a 9-year-old boy presented with similar symptoms, and the diagnosis was confirmed with X-rays and MRI. Both children were referred to the National Cancer Institute for further treatment. Another unusual case involved paired fractures in newborns, which occurred after mothers unknowingly caused the injuries by performing a traditional test on the babies. These rare fractures, occurring in the shoulder and hip, were treated using conservative methods, leading to full recovery due to the high regenerative capacity of bone tissue in infants. A third case involved two children diagnosed with Grisel-Burge syndrome, a rare condition related to inflammatory torticollis due to purulent diseases of the nasopharynx. Both children showed similar symptoms, were diagnosed with right-sided paratonsillar abscesses, and underwent surgical removal of the abscess, followed by recovery. The findings highlight the importance of recognizing paired events in medical practice, as they provide insight into trends that can aid in the early detection, diagnosis, and treatment of rare diseases. The study emphasizes the necessity of vigilance and careful observation, especially in paediatric orthopaedics and traumatology, to effectively manage these rare conditions.

Key words: Paired events, osteogenic sarcoma, paediatric orthopaedics, traumatology, Grisel-Burge syndrome, rare musculoskeletal pathologies.

Реферат. Процайло М. Д., Зубніна Ю. О., Грех А. Г., Свистун Р. В., Король В. В., Гоциньський П. В. **ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ПАРНИХ ВИПАДКІВ РІДКІСНИХ ПАТОЛОГІЙ У ДИТЯЧІЙ ОРТОПЕДІЇ ТА ТРАВМАТОЛОГІЇ.** Закон парних подій, спостережуваний у різних медичних умовах, відноситься до феномену, коли після спостереження рідкісної або надзвичайної події схожі випадки мають тенденцію виникати протягом короткого часу. Цей тренд особливо виражений у таких галузях, як педіатрична ортопедія та травматологія. Метою дослідження є вивчення таких парних подій, зокрема рідкісних патологій опорно-рухового апарату у дітей. Дослідження проаналізувало амбулаторні та стаціонарні записи пацієнтів Тернопільської обласної дитячої клінічної лікарні, застосовуючи методи, такі як рентгенографія, МРТ та класичні морфометричні техніки для спостереження за тенденціями у рідкісних клінічних випадках. Дослідження виявило кілька випадків парних випадків, зокрема двох дітей з остеогенним саркомою стегна, діагностованих протягом двох місяців. Один випадок стосувався 17-річної дівчини з вираженими симптомами, включаючи канцерозну кахексію та сильний біль у нозі, діагноз - остеогенна саркома. Через два місяці 9-річний хлопчик проявив схожі симптоми, і діагноз був підтверджений за допомогою рентгену та МРТ. Обоє дітей направили до Національного інституту раку для подальшого лікування. Інший незвичайний випадок стосувався парних переломів у новонароджених, які сталися після того, як матері ненавмисно спричинили травми, виконуючи традиційний тест на своїх дітей. Ці рідкісні переломи, що виникли в плечі та стегні, були лікувані за допомогою консервативних методів, що призвело до повного відновлення завдяки високій регенеративній здатності кісткової тканини у немовлят. Третій випадок стосувався двох дітей, діагностованих синдромом Грізеля-Бурже, рідкісним захворюванням, що пов'язане з запальним патологічним положенням голови через гнійні захворювання носоглотки. Обидві дитини проявили схожі симптоми, були діагностовані з правобічним параминдаликовим абсцесом і пройшли хірургічне видалення абсцесу, після чого швидко одужали. Висновки дослідження підкреслюють важливість виявлення парних подій у медичній практиці, оскільки вони дають змогу виявляти тенденції, що можуть допомогти у ранньому виявленні, діагностиці та лікуванні рідкісних захворювань. Дослідження наголошує на необхідності пильності та ретельного спостереження, особливо в педіатричній ортопедії та травматології, для ефективного управління цими рідкісними станами.

Ключові слова: парні випадки, остеогенна саркома, дитяча ортопедія, травматологія, синдром Грізеля-Бурже, рідкісні патології опорно-рухового апарату.

The law of paired events is a phenomenon in which once one has seen a certain event of a

rare occurrence or exceptionally rare occurrence, the same event will occur soon. This conditional rule implies the possibility of similar rare incidents to repeat themselves after the first one. The mechanism that causes this phenomenon has not been well understood but there are a number of hypotheses that have been put forward. To begin with, the increased vigilance, which accompanies the identification of a rare occurrence, makes medical practitioners more sensitive to similar events, thus more likely to identify similar occurrences. Secondly, there may be a statistical trend: in the case of a large number of observations studied, the rare occurrence can repeat, and be treated as a pattern. It is especially common in the practice of emergency medical services, such as ambulance services, emergency departments, trauma units, surgical and intensive care units, in which, once an initial rare occurrence has been treated, more similar cases are noticed within a short period of time [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

The purpose of the work is to explore the trends in paired cases in the daily practice of medical workers, in the field of the work of paediatric orthopaedics and traumatology, in particular, in the timely detection, treatment, and prevention of different musculoskeletal pathologies.

Materials and methods

The outpatient and inpatient records of children who underwent examination and treatment at the Ternopil Regional Children Clinic Hospital- a municipal non-profit organization of the Ternopil Regional Council- were studied in detail. The information gathered gives a further insight into the recurring trends in the fields of traumatology and orthopaedics.

The methods used in the research included classical morphometric methods, which allow conducting a fine evaluation of structural alterations in tissues and organs of the patients. X-ray investigations were also conducted using a standard X-ray machine to take conventional X-ray images which led to the derivation of clear images to be analyzed further. Also, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used to have a more detailed image of the internal organs and tissues as the use of a Hitachi AIRIS Mate Open-Bore 0.2T MRI device provided high accuracy in imaging and made it easier to obtain more detailed diagnostic data.

The elements of the multimodal diagnostic method aid the effective investigation and classification of the paired cases, thus leading to the increased treatment and prevention of the orthopaedic and traumatological diseases in the children.

Results of the work and their discussion

We analysed clinical cases that had the same aetiopathogenesis and occurred within a short period of time. Similar clinical presentation, course of the disease, and virtually identical treatment tactics are like copies that occur in several patients. This applied to both orthopaedic pathology and injuries. If such cases are observed frequently, then this is a pattern; if not frequently, then they are paired cases. Paired cases of rare osteogenic sarcoma of the femur. Girl N., age 17. She accidentally hit her knee while walking. She experienced minor pain in her leg, which gradually intensified over two months, especially at night. On examination, the girl's general condition was serious. She was exhausted, dehydrated, immobile, and depressed. Her skin was grey. Her eyes were deeply sunken, she had lost a lot of weight, and her nose was pointed - cancer cachexia. She limped heavily on her left leg, and the slightest movement caused unbearable pain in her leg. She cannot straighten her knee. The lower third of her left thigh is severely deformed in the form of a large spindle, the skin over the tumour is tense, hot, with a pronounced venous network. The peripheral lymph nodes are not enlarged. No pathological changes were found on the overview X-ray of the lungs. X-ray images of the knee joint reveal tumour growth around the bone, cancerous periostitis, a needle-like reaction of the periosteum on the posterior surface of the thigh, destruction and osteomalacia of the distal metaphysis of the thigh. An MRI of the knee joint showed diffuse infiltration, swelling of the bone marrow of the distal knee. The diagnosis was: osteogenic sarcoma of the distal end of the left thigh, osteoblastic component, reactive synovial effusion. The child was immediately referred to the National Cancer Institute in Kyiv for further treatment.

Two months later, a similar case with the same disease was examined in the same city in a 9-year-old boy named V. Six days earlier, he had injured his right knee and felt pain in his leg. His thigh quickly swelled, he developed a limp, and experienced unbearable pain, especially at night. Painkillers and injections did not help. X-rays of the right knee joint showed a typical picture of OS - destruction of the femur, cancerous periostitis, spicules. An overview X-ray of the lungs showed multiple metastases near the roots of both lungs. The extremely aggressive course of the disease and multiple metastases in the lungs in such a short period of observation were surprising.

Diagnosis established. Osteogenic sarcoma of the distal end of the right femur, osteoblastic component, reactive synovial effusion. Multiple metastases in the lungs. Referred to the National Cancer Institute.

There were also cases of paired fractures of the femur and humerus in newborns. Extremely rare multiple fractures were observed in newborns. The child was a firstborn, aged 1 month. The mother independently checked the condition of the child's limb joints using a proven 'old-fashioned' method. There is a popular belief that a healthy child should be able to reach the knee joint of the opposite leg with the elbow of the bent arm, which is what was done. During the 'check' using this method, the mother felt a crunch in the baby's right shoulder and left hip. The child was restless for two days, cried, refused to eat, and reacted with crying to passive movements of his legs and arms. On the third day after the mother's 'examination,' pronounced swelling of the right shoulder and left hip was detected, and the slightest movements caused the child to cry loudly and become restless. An X-ray revealed spiral fractures of the middle third of the left hip and right shoulder with displacement of the fragments. Diagnosis: Closed spiral fracture of the middle third of the right shoulder with displacement of fragments. Closed oblique-transverse fracture of the middle third of the left thigh with displacement of fragments. The parents, who were from a village, may not have had sufficient information about routine examinations of children by family doctors and paediatricians. Therefore, it was surprising when a similar 'unfortunate' case occurred 7 days later with a boy aged 1 month and 9 days from the regional centre. The mother checked the child's joints using the same method as in the first case, resulting in fractures of the left shoulder and right thigh with displacement of the fragments. During the examination, the child was restless and cried when passive movements of the limbs were attempted. There was severe swelling and pain in the left shoulder and right hip. The X-ray showed spiral fractures of the middle third of the left hip and right shoulder with displacement of the fragments. Diagnosis: Closed spiral fracture of the middle third of the left shoulder with displacement of fragments. Closed oblique-transverse fracture of the middle third of the right thigh with displacement of fragments.

Similar cases of torticollis Grisel-Bourge. A 10-year-old boy was treated for tonsillitis in the district for a week, but without success. He continued treatment at a regional facility. The child's general condition deteriorated despite intensive therapy. His general condition was moderate, with all signs of inflammatory disease - high temperature, anaemia, leukocytosis, and a left shift in the leukocyte formula. The throat was inflamed, and the back of the throat was protruding. The submandibular lymph nodes were enlarged and painful when pressed. The head is tilted to the right, and the slightest movement to the side causes severe pain. To clarify the diagnosis, an MRI of the cervical spine was performed. A large abscess was found between the base of the skull and the cervical vertebrae. Curvature of the spine in the opposite direction from the abscess due to muscle contracture and arthritis in the cervical spine (painful contracture). Initial signs of brainstem encephalitis. Diagnosis: Right-sided paratonsillar abscess. Grisel-Bourge syndrome (Grisel's torticollis). Initial signs of brainstem encephalitis. Surgical removal of the abscess was performed. Intensive course of antibiotic therapy. The child recovered quickly and was discharged home after a week.

Nine days later, a 7-year-old boy from the same city was admitted to our clinic with similar symptoms of Grisel-Bourge syndrome. Considering the previous case, we immediately performed an MRI scan and found a large abscess between the base of the skull and the cervical vertebrae. Diagnosis: right-sided paratonsillar abscess. Grisel-Bourge syndrome (Grisel torticollis). After surgical removal of the focus of inflammation and massive antibiotic therapy, the child quickly recovered and was discharged home after a week.

As a rule, osteogenic sarcoma is rare, but in our case, we observed two paired cases from the same city within two weeks. Tumour diagnosis is the most difficult and responsible area of oncology. The intellectual potential of the doctor, his experience and intuition play a dominant role in making the diagnostic process creative and accurate [7, 8, 9]. Osteogenic sarcoma most often occurs during puberty. It is a tumour of young age, with isolated cases occurring after the age of 40. Boys are affected twice as often as girls. Most often, osteogenic sarcoma is located in the knee joint (distal metaphysis of the femur, proximal metaphysis of the tibia) [10]. The disease begins suddenly, in the midst of complete health. The pain is unbearable and is poorly relieved by analgesics and narcotics. The affected limb quickly 'swells' and the child quickly becomes exhausted - cancer cachexia, severe intoxication against a background of high temperature. A complete blood count is characterised by low haemoglobin levels, an increase in the number of leukocytes and band neutrophils, which can

sometimes be interpreted as manifestations of acute haematogenous osteomyelitis. In fact, after three months, multiple metastases to the lungs are observed in 95% of cases. Metastases to other bones are rare; the tumour spreads through the arterial blood supply network. X-ray examination, which is available in any clinic, is fundamental and extremely important. Destruction of the metaphyses of long tubular bones, cancerous periostitis, multiple spicules, and tumour invasion into surrounding tissues are indisputable signs of the most malignant bone tumour.

Multiple fractures of long tubular bones in children aged 1 month are extremely rare and practically not described in medical literature, when the mother unconsciously inflicted such severe injuries on her children. According to the canons of forensic medical examination, such fractures are considered severe. Bones at this age are extremely elastic and have a strong periosteum, so it is extremely difficult to break them, but it is possible, as practice has shown. The mother checked the condition of her child's limb joints using what she believed to be a tried and tested 'old-fashioned' method, resulting in fractures of the shoulder and hip on different sides. Given the extremely high regeneration of bone tissue in children of this age, in both cases, conservative methods were used to eliminate bone displacement and achieve complete fusion.

Grisel-Burge syndrome, or Grisel-Burge syndrome, is not common in the practice of a paediatric orthopaedic traumatologist [11]. The essence of this disease is that purulent diseases of the nasopharynx, ears, and teeth are provoked by inflammatory changes in the muscles of the cervical spine and inflammation of the joints between the base of the skull and the cervical vertebrae. A persistent inflammatory contracture develops, causing an abnormal, forced position of the head - inflammatory torticollis. It is difficult to diagnose using conventional examination methods, so treatment is delayed, which can be complicated by brainstem encephalitis. The uniqueness of these two paired cases lies in the fact that two children, practically the same age, from the same city, with the same disease and the same treatment tactics - surgical removal of the abscess with complete recovery. Dispensary observation over the course of a year did not reveal any deviations in the children's development.

Conclusions

Studying rare cases that may recur in practical activity increases alertness and readiness for their diagnosis. Analysis and observation of these cases contributes to the improvement of professional skills. Studying extraordinary, rare cases increases the psychological readiness and confidence of the doctor's actions and reduces stress levels.

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